

The Scenario Exploration System: An overview

What is the Scenario Exploration System?

The Scenario Exploration System (SES) is an interactive and approachable foresight tool developed by the European Commission Joint Research Center based on a serious gaming methodology.

The game format allows participants to interact with different future realities and waves of change and to imagine how to respond. By taking on the role of different societal actors, participants are encouraged to have forward-looking discussions, develop strategies to meet long-term objectives, learn to understand and cooperate with other stakeholders and experiment how they can plan action to shape a better future - individually and collectively.

The game is highly versatile and tailorable to a variety of topics of interests and contexts.

Introduction

The Scenario Exploration System (SES) is an **interactive foresight gaming tool**. It provides a platform that engages a group of participants in **future-oriented systemic thinking** around a topic of interest.

The game aims to make participants **take action to reach their long-term objectives** in contrasting scenario-related contexts while interacting with other stakeholders. By creating a realistic journey towards the future, the SES generates a safe space to **stimulate possible responses** connected to the issue of interest and to lead to a **forward-looking discussions and decision-making**.

As an engagement platform, the SES helps to imagine plausible futures, to understand what opportunities and challenges lie ahead and what they could mean for individuals and organizations. Ultimately it encourages to think and experiment with what decisions need to be taken in order to shape the future we want.

The SES and can be used in a variety of context for different purposes, including awareness raising, educational purposes, increasing preparedness, strategic development or anticipatory governance.

In summary, the SES:

- is a future simulation tool to engage in **scenario exploration and systemic thinking**
- helps understand the **complexity of decision making**
- allows to experience different societal roles e.g. business representative, policy maker, civil society organization etc.
- is **adaptable** to a wide range of topics and contexts

Spotlight: what is foresight?

Foresight is the discipline of exploring, anticipating and shaping the future. It is based on systematic examination of information to **detect early signs** of important developments. can be defined as a sensitive exercise - using quantitative and/or qualitative methods - oriented towards the future with the aim to shape a more sustainable world.

Qualitative foresight is useful for the elaboration of long-term visions having a broad sociopolitical scope such as medium- to long-term policy strategies.

Leveraging a research-based, serious-gaming methodology, the SES makes engaging in a foresight exercise easy, approachable and entertaining for any context and group of participants, from students and citizens to senior experts and professionals.

How it works

The SES engages participants in taking on and building a societal role (e.g. policy maker, business, civil society organization etc.) and creating unique stories while exploring possible futures. The roles taken by participants can be their actual roles or they can be imagined.

Participants play by taking a series of **actions to reach the long-term objectives** of their role; some participants also take the role of public voices who observe and assess the impacts of the actions taken.

Key rules

- The game takes a **minimum of 2 hours** to explore 1 scenario and 3 hours to complete 2 scenarios. The highest impact is achieved by exploring 2 opposing/contrasting scenarios
- Every game session involves **5-7 players** facilitated by **one game master**
- Play consists of three rounds in which players are given a set of circumstances that unfold at 10, 20 and 30 years into the timeline, and must decide how they will respond
- The game can be run in person as well as digitally

5 -7 participants

1 game master

2 hours per scenario

What's in it for you?

SES outcomes include both **planned and serendipitous learnings**. While each experience is unique, participants gain a deeper understanding of global challenges and sustainable development, the need for collaboration as well as the importance of change agency and individual and collective action.

Companies:

- Helping managers to anticipate a particular future and to support strategy development, decision-making and risk management
- Generating innovative and creative ideas and supporting intrapreneurship and change agency
- Stakeholder engagement and impact management

Higher education institutions

- Integrating the tool into teaching modules to increase student engagement and futures literacy
- Using the tool within the executive team for strategic discussions and decision-making towards sustainability transition

Policymakers and civil society

- Engaging in forward-looking discussions that can feed into coordinated policy making
- Public imagination and desirable futures motivate useful sociotechnical developments
- Bringing together societal actors around one or more imagined futures leads to sharing and performing common orientations for action

Further learnings:

- A broader view of value creation and impact: actions have indirect consequences and their perception by stakeholders needs to be taken into account
- Realising the need - and the challenge - of both taking personal responsibility and adapting in response to a changing context
- Recognising the importance and options for collaborating with others
- At each point in time, all societal actors play a part in creating the future and become change agents
- Systemic thinking: understanding our world as a single, interconnected system: ecological, social, economic, psychological, and technological

Where was it used?

- **Public bodies and international organizations:** European Commission DG SANTE, European Commission DG AGRI, European Commission JRC (Bioeconomy unit), City of Frankfurt, OECD
- **Companies:** The Colruyt Group (main Belgian food retailer), The Dutch Royal Airforce, Uber
- **Civil Society Organizations:** Friends of the Earth, Junior Enterprises Europe, SCO Linköping
- **EU projects:** Eu-Innovate, NANO2ALL, Circular Ocean
- **Higher education institutions:** Cranfield Business School, Copenhagen Business School, Free University Brussels, Henley Business School, Hochschule Bremen, Jönköping International Business School, Kent Business School, Kozminski University, Liverpool John Moores University, Manchester Metropolitan University, Politecnico di Milano, Politecnico di Torino, University of Stellenbosch, University of Westminster

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Interested to learn more?

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About ABIS

ABIS - The Academy of Business in Society is a business-academic network working to advance the role of business in society through research and education. Our ambition is to make a significant contribution to the debate and the practice involved in equipping current and future business leaders with the knowledge, skills and capabilities for the long-term success of business in society.

The Academy of Business in Society

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